

Research Paper

Evaluating the Effectiveness of Traditional Leaders in Curbing Land Grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria

Brown Ruth Amiye
ruthb9987@gmail.com
Dr. Chidinma Dokubo
chidinma.dokubo@ust.edu.ng

&

Dr. Ebere Sampson Wagbara
ebere.wagbara@ust.edu.ng

Faculty of Education, Department of Adult Education and Community Development, and Department of Educational Foundations, Rivers State University.

Corresponding Author: Brown Ruth Amiye

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ABSTRACT:The study evaluated the effectiveness of traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design; three research questions guided the study. The population of the study consisted of all 423 registered community development committee (CDC) leaders in the area. Purposive sampling techniques were adopted to arrive at the sample size of 150 CDC leaders in the study. The instrument for data collection was a researcher-structured questionnaire titled: Evaluating Community Development Committee Leaders on the Effectiveness of Traditional Leaders in Curbing Land Grabbing Questionnaire. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach's Alpha reliability method. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. The findings of the study showed that traditional leaders are corrupt in curbing land grabbing, most CDC leaders agreed that social dynamics affect traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing. In addition, the respondents agreed that traditional leaders' roles in mobilising community resistance affect land grabbing

Key Words: Curbing, evaluation, effectiveness, grabbing

I. Introduction

Land is a finite and critical resource essential for various socio-economic activities, including agriculture, industrial development, housing, and environmental sustainability. In Nigeria, as in many other developing countries, the management and use of land are intrinsically tied to issues of governance, policy formulation, and socio-economic development. With a population exceeding 200 million and rapid urbanization rates, the pressure on Nigeria's land resources has intensified, leading to widespread land use conflicts, environmental degradation, and abuse of land allocation systems (Afolabi, 2020). The implications of poor land management are far-reaching, affecting everything from food security to the displacement of communities, deforestation, desertification, and the overall health of the country's ecosystems (Bakarare, 2022). Land, as a critical natural resource, plays a pivotal role in the economic and social development of Nigeria. However, its management has been fraught with challenges, particularly land use abuse, which includes illegal land acquisitions, deforestation, unsustainable agricultural practices, and urban sprawl. Effective land use monitoring and management are essential for environmental sustainability and socio-economic growth. Good ascendency, coupled with well-implemented policies, is fundamental in tackling

*Corresponding Author: Brown Ruth Amiye

ruthb9987@gmail.com

Faculty of Education,

Department of Adult Education and Community Development,

and Department of Educational Foundations, Rivers State University.

these issues. Land in Nigeria has been governed by complex and often inefficient legal and administrative systems that have contributed to its mismanagement. One of the most significant laws governing land in Nigeria is the Land Use Act of 1978. While the act was intended to standardize land ownership, democratize access to land, and ensure that land serves the public interest, it has, in practice, aggravated problems of land tenure insecurity, corruption, and inefficient land use (Okeke, 2018). This is largely due to leadership failures, a lack of transparency, and weak institutional frameworks responsible for enforcing land use policies. Over time, these challenges have led to widespread abuse in the allocation, use, and management of land across the country, especially in urban areas and resource-rich regions like Rivers State (Ojo & Adebayo, 2019). At the heart of the land use dilemma in Rivers State is the issue of traditional leaders. Traditional leaders are crucial to the proper management of land resources, as it ensures that land is allocated fairly, used sustainably, and protected from illegal exploitation. Traditional leaders are agents of change who can facilitate community development by promoting social cohesion, economic growth, and human well-being. Corroborating the above assertion, Okeke and Ibeanu (2018) affirmed that traditional leaders possess unique qualities that enable them to navigate complex social dynamics and build trust among community members. As observed by Eke (2019), traditional leaders are key stakeholders in community development and peace building, and their roles should be recognized and supported in discouraging land-grabbing activities.

Ojo and Adebayo, (2019) explained that land grabbing is an illegal acquisition of land through intimidation, force, or fraud, often involving land barons and corrupt officials, leading to disputes with legitimate owners and communities. This can include the unlawful selling of land, demolition of existing properties, and the seizure of ancestral lands for private development, sometimes with the complicity of security agents. The issue of land grabbing in Rivers State has been aggravated by the state's rich natural resources, including oil and gas. According to Kelechukwu (2020), the oil and gas industry has been a major driver of land grabbing in the state, with companies often using their influence and resources to acquire land from local communities. Dlamini-Nyagi (2020) noted that this has led to the displacement of many communities, who are forced to leave their ancestral lands to make way for oil and gas exploration. The impact of land grabbing on the environment has also been significant. He further highlights the destruction of forests, wetlands, and other ecosystems as a result of land-grabbing activities. Overall, the issue of land grabbing in Rivers State, especially in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, requires urgent attention, and the state government must take decisive action to protect the rights of local communities and prevent further environmental degradation.

Traditional leaders are often seen as custodians of communal land and cultural heritage, play a pivotal role in either facilitating or discouraging land grabbing activities. It is against this background that this study is designed to evaluate the effect of traditional leaders' roles in curbing land-grabbing activities among community inhabitants in Obio/Akpor local government, Rivers State. The phenomenon of land grabbing has become a pervasive issue in Rivers State, Nigeria, with far-reaching consequences for community inhabitants' socio-economic and environmental well-being. Despite traditional leaders' critical role in maintaining social order and promoting community development, their efforts to discourage land grabbing have been poorly reported as such assumed to be ineffective, leading to widespread displacement, destruction of ancestral lands, and erosion of cultural heritage (Amadi & Ogidi, 2024). The persistence of land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Rivers State has severe implications for community inhabitants' livelihoods and well-being, including increased poverty, food insecurity, and social unrest, leading to the destruction of lives and properties. However, traditional leaders play vital roles in upholding peace, unity, and preservation of customs and cultures through roles such as custodians of communal land, mobilizing community resistance, educating communities about land rights, utilizing cultural and spiritual values, promoting transparency in land transactions, conflict mediation, and collaboration with external stakeholders (Ogidi & Abdulahman, 2025). There are many reasons for traditional leaders' failure in curbing land grabbing, as observed by the researcher; some of these problems are that traditional leaders often lack formal training in modern land management techniques, such as surveying and the use of Geographical Information Systems (GIS). This is compounded by the fact that many traditional land transactions are poorly documented, leading to vague boundaries and frequent disputes that are difficult to resolve using conventional methods. Also, the traditional institutions have become susceptible to political interference and corruption. The quest for quick riches and personal aggrandizement has led many

traditional leaders to now align themselves with the political class, thereby jettisoning their traditional functions (land dispute mediation) to the whims and caprices of the political class. This makes communities less likely to accept their mediation in land disputes. Another crux is the issue of modernization, urbanization, and an influx of oil-related activities in the Niger Delta region (including Obio/Akpor), which have increased the complexity and value of land, leading to more frequent and intense disputes that existing traditional mechanisms may not be equipped to handle. Traditional institutions often face a deficiency of financial resources and capacity-building opportunities to effectively manage land conflicts. This limits their ability to access necessary information, organize peace education, and implement sustainable conflict resolution strategies. The researcher also observed that youth disrespect elders, partly due to the elders' perceived inability to meet basic community needs, which has contributed to a decline in the moral authority and influence of traditional leaders. This makes it harder for them to command the respect necessary to enforce communal agreements and maintain peace. It is on these notes that the researcher wants to evaluate the effectiveness of traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obi/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State Nigeria.

II. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to;

- i. Determine how traditional leaders' engagement in corruption affects land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria.
- ii. Examine how social dynamics affect traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria.
- iii. Investigate how community mobilization resistance affects traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria

III. Research question

- i. What is the effect of traditional leaders' engagement in corruption on land curbing and grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria?
- ii. How does social dynamics affect traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria
- iii. How does community mobilization resistance affect traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria

IV. Literature Review

Osaze, Ogbe, and Omoruyi (2023) examined influence of Traditional Leaders roles on Land Rights awareness among community inhabitants in Akoko-Edo Local Government Area, Edo State, Nigeria. The study among others, revealed that traditional leaders convene town hall meetings to discuss land rights, laws, and policies and allows community members to ask questions and seek clarification, organize community outreach programmes within their domain to educate community members about land rights and responsibilities, use cultural events and gatherings, such as festivals and ceremonies, to educate community members about land rights and promote awareness, and also meet with community groups, such as farmers' associations or women's groups, to educate them about land rights and provide guidance on land-related issues to a high extent, The study further recommended among others that the community authorities/leaders should collaborate with lawyers and community change agents to further raise consciousness of human rights in respect to land to empower them with knowledge to not only protect their rights, but to also respect the land rights of others to avoid temptation of being involved in grabbing activities.

Timothy T. A., Benjamin T. & Dekera, assess the level of involvement of the traditional institution in the fight against corruption and bad governance, and evaluate the approaches used by the traditional institution

in tackling corruption and bad governance. The findings of the study showed that corruption is pervasive in Benue State, yet the traditional institutions in the state have little role to play in the fight against corruption due to their limited level of involvement in the anti-corruption war. Despite this, the traditional institution has adopted some approaches like the use of taboos and superstitions to enforce fear and punish offenders, summons and counselling, the use of threats, refusal to collect corrupt gifts, insistence on morality and justice, and the use of anti-corruption emblems to fight corruption at the local level. However, due to their limited role, corruption remains pervasive in the state. The study, therefore, recommends, among others, that the government and other stakeholders should make efforts to integrate traditional approaches to curbing corruption and bad governance, while politicians should desist from engaging in corrupt activities and instead cooperate with traditional institutions to ensure socio-economic development in Benue state and Nigeria at large.

Orlu and Achinulo. (2017), worked on the traditional Administrative System and the Politics of Land Management in Akpor Kingdom, Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria. Objectives centered on evaluating the relationship between the traditional administrative system and the politics of land management in Akpor Kingdom. The findings were that there is a significant relationship between traditional administrative system and land management in Akpor Kingdom, that conflicts do arise in course of land sharing which can be resolved through process of summoning or law court and that the Nyewe-Ali in Council, the Council of Chiefs, the family heads and the committee set aside for such matters are those in charge of land management in Akpor Kingdom. The conclusion was that there is a significant relationship between the traditional administrative system and the politics of land management in Akpor Kingdom and that the traditional administrative system enhances an effective and efficient process of land management in Akpor Kingdom, through the Nyewe-Ali in Council, the council of chiefs, the family heads, and the committee set aside for such matters. The recommendations among others were; constitutional relevance should be given to the traditional rulers to enable them perform effectively and decisively on the contradictions that arise concerning land matters, that government at all levels should desist to meddle with traditional institution as it is a sacred institution and that chiefs should adjudicate matters at customary courts at local government areas, while majesties are to be in charge of customary court of appeal without government interference.

V. Methods

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The study was conducted in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. The population of the study consisted of all 423 registered community development committee (CDC) leaders in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State (Rivers State Ministry of Chieftaincy and Local Government Affairs, 2025). The choice of using community development committee leaders was effective, since CDC leaders represent the community's interests and can provide insight into the community's experiences. Also, traditional leaders may have their own interests or agenda, which could influence their responses. Purposive sampling techniques was adopted to arrive at the sample size of 150 community development committee (CDC) leaders in the communities, these communities are deduced from the four clan that constitute Obio/Akpor local government area namely: Obio, Akpor, Aparara and Rumueme, Stratified sampling technique was adopted for the sample to select five (5) communities in each of these clan for the study, simple random sampling techniques was then applied to choose 30 community development committee (CDC) leaders in each of these communities, making it a total of 150 community development committee leaders (CDC). The instrument for data collection was self-structured instruments titled: Evaluating Community Development Committee Leaders on the Effectiveness of Traditional Leaders in Curbing Land Grabbing Questionnaire (ECDCLTLCLGQ). The instrument was designed using four (4) point rating scale from "Strongly Agree" (1) to "Strongly Disagree" (4). The research instrument was validated by two experts' judgment in the Measurement and Evaluation Department of the Educational Foundations Faculty of Education, Rivers State University. These experts assessed the questionnaire items for relevance, clarity, comprehensiveness, and appropriateness. The instrument was subjected to a reliability test using Cronbach's Alpha, conducted with data from the pilot study involving 20 respondents from the Choba community development committee leaders (CDC), which is not part of the sample community. The reliability coefficient for the entire questionnaire was 0.83. The researchers sought the services of three research assistants to help them administer the questionnaires in their various communities; the completed copies of the questionnaires were retrieved immediately from the respondents. Out of the 150 copies of the questionnaire administered,

102 copies were successfully retrieved and used for analysis. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation.

VI. **Result**

Research Question 1: What is the effect of traditional leaders' engagement in corruption on land curbing and grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean Responses of CDC leaders on the effect of traditional leaders' engagement in corruption for curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government, Rivers State, Nigeria

S/N	Description	CDC leaders		
		\bar{X}	SD	Rmks
		N = 102		
1.	Traditional leaders often encounter corruption practices related to land grabbing.	2.70	0.65	Agree
2	Traditional leaders incorporate corruption values in their efforts to protect communal land from grabbers.	2.62	0.61	Agree
3	Community members respect traditional leaders' decisions regarding communal land due to their corruption.	2.77	0.54	Agree
4	Corruption affected traditional leaders' and CDC leaders' ability to address land-grabbing issues.	2.78	0.66	Agree
5	Corruption has contributed to the increase in land grabbing.	2.85	0.72	Agree
6	Community members are more likely to follow traditional leaders' guidance on land issues due to their corrupt influence	2.75	0.69	Agree
7.	Traditional leaders' use of corruption tactics has been effective in reducing land-grabbing activities.	2.88	0.76	Agree
	Grand Mean	2.76		Agree

Table 1 above for research question 1 shows the mean responses of CDC leaders on the effect of traditional leaders' engagement in corruption in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. Item 1 had mean scores of 2.70 with standard deviations of 0.65, Item 2 recorded mean scores of 2.62 with standard deviations of 0.61, and Item 3 had mean scores of 2.77 with standard deviations of 0.54. Item 4 had mean scores of 2.78, with a standard deviation of 0.66. Item 5 recorded mean scores of 2.85 with standard deviations of 0.72, item 6 recorded mean scores of 2.75 with standard deviations of 0.69, while item 7 had mean scores of 2.88 with standard deviations of 0.76. The grand mean scores of the respondents were 2.76 is higher than the decision mean of 2.50. It therefore implies that traditional leaders are corrupt in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: How does social dynamics affect traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria

Table 2: Mean Responses of CDC leaders on the effect of social dynamics on traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government, Rivers State, Nigeria

S/N		CDC leaders		
		\bar{X}	SD	Rmks
		N = 102		
8	Community pressure affects traditional leaders' efforts to curb land grabbing	2.70	1.22	Agree
9	Social networks impact traditional leaders' ability to address land curbing and grabbing issues	2.78	1.18	Agree
10	Community members' engagement and participation enhance the effectiveness of traditional leaders to support land grabbing.	2.86	1.13	Agree
11.	Traditional leaders' efforts promote peaceful coexistence among community members.	2.60	1.24	Agree
12	Community norms and values play an important role in shaping traditional leaders' and CDC leaders' responses to land grabbing	2.76	1.20	Agree
13	Traditional leaders collaborate with other stakeholders to resolve land conflicts.	2.71	1.17	Agree
	Grand Mean	2.74	1.19	Agree

Table 2 above for research question 2 shows the mean responses of CDC leaders on the effect of social dynamics on traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Rivers State Nigeria Item 8 had mean scores of 2.70, standard deviation of 1.22, item 9 had mean scores of 2.78, standard deviation of 1.18, item 10 had mean scores of 2.86, standard deviation of 1.13, item 11 had mean scores of 2.60, standard deviation of 1.24, item 12 had mean scores of 2.76, standard deviation of 1.18. while item 13 had mean scores of 2.71 with standard deviations of 1.17. The grand mean of 2.74 is higher than the decision mean of 2.50, which indicates that respondents were in agreement that social dynamics affect traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Question 3: How does community mobilization resistance affect traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria

Table 3: Mean Responses of CDC leaders on the effect of community mobilization resistance on traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government, Rivers State, Nigeria

S/N		CDC leaders		
		\bar{X}	SD	Rmks
		N = 102		
14	Traditional leaders in my community actively mobilise resistance against land-grabbing activities.	2.65	0.57	Agree
15	Traditional leaders organise community meetings to sensitise inhabitants about the dangers of land grabbing.	2.67	0.67	Agree
16	Traditional leaders encourage community members to report land-grabbing incidents to the authorities.	2.61	0.62	Agree
17	Traditional leaders work with community members to develop strategies to prevent land grabbing.	2.73	0.54	Agree
18	Traditional leaders use their influence to protect communal land from grabbers.	2.70	0.60	Agree
19	Community members are more likely to resist land-grabbing activities due to traditional leaders' efforts.	2.60	0.59	Agree
	Grand Mean	2.66		Agree

Table 3 above for research question 3 shows the mean responses of CDC leaders on community mobilization resistance affecting traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria. Item 14 recorded mean scores of 2.65 with standard deviation of 0.57, item 15 had mean scores of 2.67, with standard deviations of 0.67, item 16 recorded mean scores of 2.61 with standard deviation of 0.62, item 17 had mean scores of 2.73, with standard deviations of 0.54, item 18 recorded mean scores of 2.70 with standard deviations of 0.60, item 19 had mean scores of 2.68 with standard deviation of 0.59, while. Responses in this research question 3 recorded a grand mean of 2.66 respondent which is greater than the criterion mean of 2.50. The results pointed out that the respondents were in agreement that community mobilization resistance affects traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria.

VII. Discussion of Findings

Firstly, the study examined the effect of traditional leaders' engagement in corruption on land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria. It was found that traditional leaders are corrupt in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. This was shown in incorporating corruption practices, incorporating corruption values to protect communal land, making decisions regarding communal land, and cannot address land grabbing issues, contributing to the increase in land grabbing and reduced land grabbing activities due to corruption tactics. The findings of the study are in line with the findings of Afolabi and Ibrahim (2022) that community leaders are indecisive in land disputes, thereby increasing violence, inability to initiate development projects, represent community interests, and advocate for resources and services. The finding also corroborates the position of Nlerum (2019) that traditional leaders in Nigeria continue to abandon significant influence over communal lands due to the legitimacy of customary laws and their intimate understanding of local restraints. The findings

accentuate the enduring significance of traditional leaders in managing land allocation and triggering clashes. Yet, critical engagement with their roles reveals the necessity for reform that harmonises customary and statutory systems to mitigate abuse of authority and ensures that land governance serves the collective good of communities rather than entrenched benefits.

Secondly, the study investigated the effect of social dynamics on traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria. Respondents agreed that social dynamics affect traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria. The study revealed that community pressure affects traditional leaders' efforts to curb land grabbing, and social networks impact traditional leaders' ability to address land grabbing and promote peaceful coexistence among community members. Norms and values play an important role in shaping traditional leaders and CDC, and collaboration with stakeholders resolves land grabbing. The finding in research question 2 is related to the finding of Odey (2019) that traditional leaders partner with external bodies to enhance infrastructure development, promote agricultural development through cooperative societies, support education initiatives, facilitate conflict resolution and peace-building efforts, and preserve cultural heritage and traditional practices.

Thirdly, the study assessed how community mobilization resistance affects traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. The results of research question 3 pointed out that the respondents agreed that traditional leaders' roles in mobilising community resistance affects land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. Traditional leaders actively mobilise resistance against land grabbing, organise community meetings to sensitise inhabitants about the dangers of land grabbing, encourage community members to report land grabbing incidents to the authorities, work with community members to develop strategies to prevent land grabbing, use their influence to protect communal land from grabbers, and that community members are more likely to resist land grabbing due to traditional leaders' efforts. This finding affirmed the position of Adikwu, and Odey (2020) that traditional leaders have significant influence in mobilising community resistance due to their deep connection to local culture and customs which enables them to rally community members and facilitate collective action, The finding in this research question 3 also correlates with the finding of Eze (2020) that the authority of traditional leaders enables the rapid organisation of communal demonstrations and legal challenges, creating significant social and operational costs for potential grabbers. This collective action, rooted in traditional structures of solidarity, serves as a powerful deterrent. Corroborating this, Amadi (2022) finds that the mere threat of unified opposition, publicly championed by the chief, is often sufficient to cause speculators to abandon their encroachment plans, thereby preserving communal land.

VIII. Conclusion

The study evaluates the effectiveness of traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. The variables of the study include: Traditional leaders' engagement in corruption affects land grabbing, how social dynamics affect traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing, and how community mobilization resistance affects traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing. The result of the analyses indicated that most of the traditional leaders are corrupt in curbing land grabbing. Agree that social dynamics affect traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing, and that community mobilization resistance affects traditional leaders in curbing land grabbing, which has seriously hampered their ability to act effectively and authoritatively as gatekeepers of their community

IX. Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

1. The government should put in place, most especially, at the state and local government levels, to formalize the adoption of a traditional approach to curbing land-grabbing corruption
2. Traditional leaders should be encouraged to mediate in conflicts in the community and should be educated on modern and alternative dispute resolution in curbing land-grabbing.
3. Traditional leaders should collaborate with community development committees, youth groups, and women's organizations to mobilise resistance against land grabbing

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